

EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN INSURANCE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Employees – the vital part of the organisation should be developed as they are contributing for the organization's success. An organisation requires the employees of highly skilled, knowledgeable with right attitude for its smooth functioning and development. Training is the important managerial function in any organisation to educate / impart knowledge to the employees about their work in which they are involved. The training brings tremendous change in the employee's skill level, knowledge and performance. Insurance industry is the important one in providing employees training and the performance of the employees very much relies on the training provided to them. The insurance sector in India has gone through a number of phases by allowing private companies to solicit insurance and also allowing foreign direct investment of up to 26% earlier and 49% from 2012. Insurance sector requires employees who have strong critical thinking skills, the ability to get the most out of people and the ability to rise where everybody is. Training and development is of paramount importance at this juncture. As any other industry in the growth phase, the insurance industry has the capacity to create a large number of job opportunities. Training requirements in the insurance sector vary according to levels in the organization. The most frequently delivered training modules in the industry are designed for sales managers and agents. These modules emphasize on sales effectiveness, product knowledge, sales communication and relevant technology. The ones for non-sales staff are typically technical in nature, while senior management is trained on regulatory and corporate governance aspects. The present study made an effort to analyse the training and development initiatives in the Indian insurance sector.

Keywords: Training, Organisation, Employees, Performance, Insurance

INTRODUCTION

The insurance sector has gone through a number of phases by allowing private companies to solicit insurance and also allowing increased foreign direct investment from 26% to 49% in 2012. Indian Insurance sector was thrown open to competition in 2000 and has evolved since then; thanks to robust regulatory framework, positive business Environment and economic growth. Government-owned Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India is the country's largest insurer, controlling approximately 65 per cent of the market. Life insurance penetration in India is about 4.4 per cent of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) in terms of total premiums underwritten annually, according to the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA).

Training and development is of paramount importance at this juncture. As any other industry in the growth phase, the insurance industry has the capacity to create a large number of job opportunities. Training requirements in the insurance industry vary according to levels in the organization. People in the insurance industry may be segmented into sales, non-sales and senior management/ board. Training programs may be designed accordingly. The most frequently delivered training modules in the industry are designed for sales managers and agents. These modules emphasize on sales effectiveness, product knowledge, sales communication and relevant technology. The ones for non-sales staff are typically technical in nature, which senior management is trained on regulatory and corporate governance aspects.

TRAINING PROCEDURES FOLLOWED IN THE INSURANCE SECTOR

Training and development is the field which is concerned with organizational activity aimed at bettering the performance of individuals and groups in organizational settings. It has been known by several names, including human resource development, and learning and development. Training and development (T&D) encompasses three main activities: training, education, and development.

- **Training:** This activity is both focused upon, and evaluated against, the job that an individual currently holds
- **Education:** This activity focuses upon the jobs that an individual may potentially hold in the future, and is evaluated against those jobs.
- **Development:** This activity focuses upon the activities that the organization employing the individual, or that the individual is part of, may partake in the future, and is almost impossible to evaluate.

Favourable economic climate and number of other factors such as, growing urbanization, increasing consumerism, rise in the standard of living, increase in financial services for people living in rural areas, etc has increased the demand for wide range of financial products that has led to mutually beneficial growth to the **insurance** sector and economic growth process. This was coincided by technology development in the insurance operations.

Following table represents the various types of training modules administered across different levels in the insurance sector.

Organizational Level / Department	Training Modules Administered
Sales staff/agents	Sales effectiveness, Product knowledge, Communication, Using IT, Problem solving
Non Sales staff	Business environment, Operational Policies, Product concept and design, Underwriting, Actuary, After sales service, Compliance, Settlement process and fraud investigation
Board/ Senior Management	Solvency, Capital requirements, Corporate Governance, Regulatory / audit Compliance, Risk Management

Source : www.irdaindia.org

Types of training given in insurance sector include:

- Skills training
- Refresher training
- Cross functional training
- Team training
- Orientation training

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Training and Development basically deals with the acquisition of understanding, know how, techniques and practices. In fact, training and development is one of the imperatives of human resource management as it can improve performance at individual, collegial and organizational levels. As the process of ‘increasing one’s capacity to take action, organizations are now increasingly becoming particular with organizational learning and therefore collective development. Organizational learning, on the other hand, refers to the “efficient procedure to process, interpret and respond to both internal and external information of a predominantly explicit nature.

According to Easterby-Smith (1999), the emergence of the concept of organizational learning is central on the hitherto idea that prior advocacies of learning are tended to its commercial significance and are lacking of empirical information on learning processes. Strategically, organizational learning, which makes use of training and development as one of the several responses, deals with the acquisition of understanding, know-how, techniques and practices. These intellectual intangibles can be translated into an organizational resource through the people that acquire, infer and utilize such towards the achievement of the organization-wide training and development.

Sims (2002) emphasizes that training focuses on present jobs while development prepares employees for possible future jobs. Basically, the objective of training and development is to contribute to the organization's overall goal. Closing the skills gap is now a critical area of human resource development for organizations to continuously penetrate the market. Skills gap basically threatens the productivity and competitiveness both in organizational and operational levels. This requires that human resource management professionals should start the cultivation of the workforce from the recruitment period. However, this is not easy considering that there are specific works which require customization of skills and that not all newly hired employees acquire social skills aside from the basic skills. In responding to the challenges of the skills gap and skills deficiency, HR professionals have to develop programs that will address the problem (Sims, 2006). Building the organization hence is an imperative for the existence and survival of modern organizations. Consistently, companies are investing on their internal customers or employees thus taking advantage of the human capital management. Sense of ownership is also important, requiring HR professionals to develop strategies that will ensure superior knowledge, skills and experience to settle within the workforce. Learning activities shall put skills enhancement and development assignments at its core as well as empowerment and career development. This is lifelong learning which guide the organizations particularly human resource department to make an ongoing investment with organizational members and help them build their competencies (Sims, 2006). The purposes of learning from the employee perspective are basically to acquire skills and knowledge to do the job and to gain promotion and advance career. In facilitating career changes, training and development also caters for the personal and professional developments.

A study by **Shefali Verma & Rita Goyal (2011)** analyzed the status of the various training and development practices in Life Insurance Corporation in India and explores the proposed link between the training and employees productivity. This study emphasizes the importance of training for the effective functioning of the organisation. The employee performance is measured in terms of the improvement in Productivity, Absenteeism and the Employee Job Satisfaction.

Vaasan Ammattikorkeakoulu (2013) conducted a case study to evaluate the effects of training on employee performance, using the telecommunication industry in Uganda. The study was based on three case studies of the biggest telecommunication companies operating in Uganda. A qualitative research approach of the data collection was adopted using a questionnaire comprising of 18 questions distributed to 120 respondents. Based on this sample the results obtained indicate that the training is a clear effect on the performance of employees. In the insurance sector, the training and development function holds a key responsibility by helping employees to upgrade their performance on a continuous basis.

Prasadini N Gamage & Mr. Lionel Imbulana (2013) conducted a study for identifying the effectiveness of the training and development of the call center staff of the Sri Lanka Telecom. The performance was measured with the dimensions of employees Productivity, Absenteeism

and the Job Satisfaction. The statistical analysis of the study revealed that that there is a significant positive relationship between the training & development and the employee productivity.

Hemanalini R (2013) conducted a study, to examine the impact of the training and development programs on employee performance in IBFI Federal Life Insurance Company Ltd, Coimbatore. The available evidence from descriptive research and the model were tested with a survey sample (n=200). This study carried two dimensions such as training and development and employee performance with two inter-dependent variables such as work attitude and job involvement. The data was obtained by questionnaire method and random sampling method was used. The purpose of this study was to examine and gain a better understanding of the drivers that influence the impact of training and development on the employee performance. It is found that there is a high relationship between training & development and employee performance. The factors age, tenure and marital status over employee performance is high association between each other.

According to **Amir Elnaga & Amen Imran (2013)** training plays vital role in the building of competencies of new as well as current employees to perform their job in an effective way. Their study in hand chiefly focuses on the role of training in enhancing the performance of the employees. It also prepares employees to hold future position in an organization with full capabilities and helps to overcome the deficiencies in any job related area. Training is considered as that sort of investment by the firm that not only brings high return on investment but also supports to achieve competitive advantage.

Uzma Hafeez & Waqar Akbar (2015) in their research aims to see the “Impact of Training on Employee Performance in Pharmaceutical Industry in Karachi Pakistan”, in which the training is considered as independent whereas dependent variable „Employee Performance,, having its performance areas i.e.; demonstrating team work, communication skill, customer service, interpersonal relationship and reduced absenteeism and its development areas i.e.; job-satisfaction, employee motivation, new technologies, efficiencies in process and innovation in strategies as its levers. Four pharmaceutical companies are selected. A survey of 356 employees via self administrated questionnaire with the help of random sampling technique is conducted with the response rate of 96%. The analysis shows that when the employee gets more the training, more efficient their level of performance would be.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY-

- A study on the training procedures being followed in the Insurance sector in India.
- To identify employees’ competency levels as enhanced by the training and development implemented.

INDICATIVE PHENOMENA OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

There are some organizational phenomena that are categorized as indicative phenomena at the time when a need for training and development appears. If work achievement standard is unrealized, employee will be incapable of performing his duties and unproductive, while decreasing selling rate and profit are some general indications that appear in organization. According to Belschak, F. D., & Hartog, D. N. D. (2009) seven main phenomena in organization that needs handling as follows:

- Low Productivity
- High Absenteeism
- High Turnover
- Low employee morale
- High grievances
- Strike
- Low profitability

TRAINING DESIGN PROCESS

The training design process refers to a systematic approach for developing training programs. Above Figure presents the seven steps in this process. Step 1 is to conduct a needs assessment, which is necessary to identify whether training is needed. Step 2 is to ensure that employees have the motivation and basic skills necessary to master the training content. Step 3 is to create a learning environment that has the features necessary for learning to occur. Step 4 is to ensure that trainees apply the training content to their jobs. This step involves having the trainee understand how to manage skill improvement as well as getting co-worker and manager support.

Conducting Need Assessment
Ensuring Employees' Readiness for Training
Creating a learning Environment
Ensuring Transfer of Training
Developing an Evaluation plan
Selecting Training method
Monitoring & Evaluating the Programme

STUDY ON THE TRAINING PROCEDURES BEING FOLLOWED IN THE INSURANCE SECTOR IN INDIA

The present study helped to investigate and analyse the current trends training and development initiatives adopted in the Insurance Companies. A sample size of 100 employees working in some of the well-known insurance companies was taken for the study. The major observations obtained from the study were as follows:

➤ ***Training is Conducted for All Levels of Employees***

Among 100 employees, 45 employees strongly agreed, 40 employees agreed and 15 employees disagreed with the fact that the training is being conducted for all levels of employees in the organization.

➤ ***Frequency of the Training Programmes***

Among the 100 employees surveyed 7 respondents reported that training is being organized for them once in a year, 32 employees said training is being organized for them once in every half year, 48 employees said that training is organized for them once in every quarter and 13 employees said that training programmes are organized in their company once in every month. Thus I can say that the frequency of training programmes for the employees in the Insurance Companies is generally once in every quarter and once in every half year.

➤ ***Induction Training for the Newly Recruited Employees***

Among the 100 employees who were questioned in order to find out that whether Induction Training Programmes are being organized for the newly recruited employees ,82 employees agreed and 18 disagreed .Therefore it could be inferred that all the major Insurance Companies do organize Induction Training Programmes for the newly recruited employees.

➤ ***Training Methods Being Employed***

Among the 100 employees surveyed 58 employees said that their organization adopted On the Job Training methods, 33 employees said that their organization adopted Off the Job Training methods and 9 employees said that their organization adopted both On the Job as well as Off the Job Training Methods. Thus I can say that the Insurance Companies generally follow On the Job Training Methods.

➤ ***On the Job Training Methods Being Used***

Among the 58 employees, 28 employees said that their organization makes use of Mentoring in order to provide training to the employees, 19 employees said that their organization used Coaching in order to provide training to the employees and 11 employees said that their organization used Job Instruction Training Method in order to provide training to the employees. Thus I can say that the Insurance companies generally followed Mentoring and Coaching methods in order to provide training to the employees.

➤ ***Off the Job Training Methods Being Used***

Among the 33 employees, 11 employees said that the organization makes use of Lecture Method in order to provide training to the employees, 15 employees said that their organization used Role Playing in order to provide training to the employees, 3 said their organization used Programmed Instruction Method and 4 employees said that their organization used Conferences and discussions in order to provide training to the employees. Thus I can say that the Insurance companies generally followed Role Playing and Lecture Method in order to provide training to the employees.

➤ ***Appointment of Trainer***

Among the 100 employees being surveyed, 63 employees responded that the trainers for the training programme were being appointed by the organization from outside the organization. 37 employees said that the senior employees acted as trainer for their subordinates in the organization.

➤ ***Do the Employees Attend the Training Programmes Being Organized for Them Regularly?***

76 respondents replied that they have regularly attended the training programmes being organized for them by their organization and 24 employees felt that they were irregular at the training programmes.

➤ ***Satisfaction of the Employees About the Trainers Being Selected***

77 employees were satisfied with the selection of the trainers in their organization and 23 employees were dissatisfied with the selection of the trainers in their organization.

➤ ***Areas Covered Mostly in Training***

41 employees said that their organization concentrated mostly in providing training in knowledge, 12 felt that their organization concentrates in providing training in techniques, 13 employees said that their organization provided training mainly in the area of Technical skills and 34 employees felt that their organization provided training mainly in the area of Social Skills. Thus I can say that Knowledge and Social Skills are the two areas in which the Insurance Companies provided training to the employees.

➤ ***Soft Skills Training***

87 employees said that their organization provided them Soft Skills training and 13 employees said that their organization did not provided them soft skills training. Thus I can say that the Insurance Companies did provide Soft Skills Training to their employees.

➤ ***Team Training***

63 employees said that their organization provided them Team Training whereas 37 employees said that their organization did not provided them Team Training. Thus I can say that

the Insurance Companies did provided training to their employees about various aspects of working in a team.

➤ ***Creativity Training***

29 employees said that their organization provided creativity training to their employees whereas 71 employees said that the organization did not provided creativity training to their employees. Thus I can say that the Insurance companies did provided Creativity training to the employees.

➤ ***Evaluation of Skills, Knowledge and Abilities Before Training***

79 employees said that their organization evaluated their skills, knowledge and abilities before conducting the training programmes whereas 21 employees said that their organization did not evaluated their skills, knowledge and abilities before conducting the training programmes. Thus I can say that the Insurance companies did evaluate the skills, knowledge and abilities of the employees before conducting the training programmes.

➤ ***Evaluation of Skills, Knowledge and Abilities During the Training***

31 employees said that their organization evaluated their skills, knowledge and abilities during the training programme whereas 69 employees said that the organization did not evaluated their skill, knowledge and abilities during the training programme. Thus I can say that the Insurance Companies did not evaluate the skills, knowledge and abilities of the employees during the training.

➤ ***Evaluation of Skills, Knowledge and Abilities After the Training***

58 employees said that their organization evaluated their skills, knowledge and abilities after the training programme is over whereas 42 employees said that the organization does not evaluated their skills, knowledge and abilities after the training programme. Thus I can say that the Insurance Companies did evaluate the skills, knowledge and abilities of the employees after the training programmes is over.

➤ ***Training Provided Helps in Day to Day Job Responsibilities to the Employees***

41 employees said that they were able to employ the skills, knowledge and abilities learnt in the training programmes being organized by their organization to a great extent, 25 said that they were able to employ them to some extent, 27 employees said that they employed them very little and 7 employees said that they did not employed the skills, knowledge and abilities. Thus I can say that the employees working in the Insurance companies were able to use the skills, knowledge and abilities learnt in the training programmes being organized by their organization.

➤ ***Use of Latest Technology***

31 employees said that their organization made use of latest technology in the training programmes whereas 69 employees said that their organization did not make use of latest

technology in the training programmes organized by their organization. Thus I can say that the Insurance Companies do not make use of latest technology in the training programmes.

➤ ***Employees Opinion About the Training Programme***

33 employees felt that the training programmes being organized by their organization were excellent, 25 felt it was good, 23 felt fair and 9 felt that the training programmes being organized by their organization were poor.

➤ ***Motivational Training***

87 employees said that the organization provided them motivational training whereas 13 employees said that their organization did not provided them motivational training. Thus I can say that the Insurance companies did provide Motivational training to the employees.

From the above study, I can interpret following about the training programmes in the Insurance Companies:

- Training is generally needed for all levels of employees in the insurance sector.
- Training programmes are organized usually once in quarter or once in every half year in the insurance companies based on their performance.
- Both on the Job training and off the job training methods are being employed in order to provide training to the employees.
- Role Playing and Lecture Method are the major Off the Job training methods being used in the Insurance companies.
- Induction training for the newly recruited employees is a must for the Insurance Companies.
- The trainers for the training programmes are generally appointed by the company from outside.
- Employees being satisfied with the training programmes regularly attend the training.
- Knowledge and Social Skills are the areas where the employees are trained the most.
- Employees are given only soft skills and team training. However they are not given any creativity training.
- Evaluation of the Skills, Knowledge and Abilities of the employees is done before and after the training programmes but not during the training programmes.
- The companies do not collect proper feedback from the employees about the training programmes.
- The Insurance Companies do organize Motivational Training for the employees in order to improve their performance.
- The training organized in the Insurance companies do help the help the employees in their career development and in help them to improve in carrying out their day to day job responsibilities.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS-

Following recommendations can be given from the study carried out on the training procedures being followed in the Insurance Sector:

- Proper record of the training programmes should be maintained.
- Creativity training should be introduced for the employees as it helps them to discover their talents.
- Proper Motivational training should be organized. Motivational training thus forms an important aspect to enhance the performance of the employees in the Insurance sector.
- Regular feedback should be collected from the employees about the training programmes and a proper record should be maintained. This is because the feedback serves as an important source to find out what are the flaws in the current training procedures and recording them would help to eliminate the same in the future.

The companies should try to employ potential in-house trainers as they understand employee needs in a much better way.

CONCLUSION

In mature and increasingly regulated markets, performance directed training is gaining in prevalence. This is due to relatively higher job mobility being seen by the insurance industry in life, non-life and health sector in addition to Broking and Third Party administrators. The current need for specialisation in underwriting, policy writing, and claims management if addressed, will go a long way in enhancing competency development. Best practices are no longer a matter of professional practice, but of compliance as well. Training is a learning process that involves acquisition of knowledge, sharpening of skills concepts, rules, or changing of attitudes and behaviors to enhance the performance. The need of the hour is to enhance insurance literacy to empower consumers to make informed decisions based on available choices. Further ,insurance industry must evince a commitment to insurance education; to develop professionalism within insurance stakeholders who have a decisive role to play in ensuring the distribution of the fruits of insurance to every nook and corner of this vast country. Training and development can be defined as planned effort from the organization to improve staff's knowledge, skills and competence. Training and development are two same concepts, i.e. to improve knowledge, skills and capabilities. However, concerning on the objectives, these two concepts are distinguishable. Training is focused more on capability improvement for current specific purposes, while development is focused more on knowledge improvement for future job where the process is carried out in integrative ways with other activities to better work behavior. Training Need Analysis (TNA) is a workplace needs analysis specifically intended to find what

actually training needs as the priority. Information of the needs will help organization in making use of resources (fund, time, etc.) in effective as well to prevent unnecessary training activity.

REFERENCES

- Ameer-ul-Ameer, Hanif F. Superior University Lahore, Journal of Business Studies Quarterly 2013.
- Andrews G, Russell M. Employability skills development : strategy , evaluation and impact 2012.
- Asmaak L, Corresponding S. Employability Awareness among Malaysian Undergraduates 2010.
- Decenzo, Robbins. Human Resource Management, Wiley, 8th Edition 2007.
- Elnaga A, Imran A. European Journal of Business and Management 2013.
- Farooq M, Md. Khan A. Impact of Training and Feedback on Employee Performance. Far East Journal of Psychology and Business 2011.
- Gamage PN, Imbulana L. International Journal of Marketing, Finance Service & Management Research 2013; 2(9).
- Hemanalini R. Analysis of Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance at Life Insurance Company. IJSR - International Journal of Scientific Research 2013.
- Hafeez U, Md. Jinnah A. Impact of Training on Employees Performance (Evidence from Pharmaceutical Companies in Karachi, Pakistan). Business Management and Strategy 2015.
- Kutty S, Misra P. IC 33 Life Insurance, Insurance Institute of India, Mumbai, 2012.
- Korkeakoulu V, Nassazi A. Effects of training on Employee performance. Evidence from Uganda, Koskinen Ossi.
- Verma S, Goyal R. A Study of Training in Insurance and their Impact On Employees Productivity. International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences 2011.
- www.bajajallianz.com
- www.bharti-axalife.com
- www.hdfclife.com
- www.lic.com
- www.irdaindia.org